

COMPUTATIONAL ANALYSIS OF FIBRE-REINFORCED THERMOPLASTIC SHEETS IN A CONTINUOUS FORMING PROCESS

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INTRODUCTION

Continuous fibre reinforced thermoplastic sheets are well suited to rapid, mass production forming technologies. Unfortunately, the majority of processing methods have fallen somewhat short of what was originally anticipated at the time of their commercial inception. This can be attributed to the relatively high capital costs incurred at the manufacturing stage, and the fixation, in many circles, with labour intensive processes. However, one of the few processing technologies to emerge in recent times, which looks likely to realise the benefits of thermoplastic composite sheets is roll forming. Borrowed from sheet metal forming, roll forming is a highly versatile and productive process with lines speeds as high as 10 m.min⁻¹ already achieved. As illustrated in Figure 1, the process involves passing a flat sheet through a series of rolls which gradually deform the material into some desirable profile. The complexity of the forming mechanism, and the limited understanding of material behaviour are key issues that have to be addressed if the technology is to undergo a successful transition from sheet metals to FRTPs. Modelling the complex forming path, and identifying potentially problematic areas is clearly desirable.

Fig. 1: A schematic diagram of the roll forming process.

In this paper we introduce the computational framework for analysing continuous fibre-reinforced thermoplastic sheets in a steady state forming process such as roll forming. After briefly reviewing the kinematic relations, and stress equilibrium equations for large deformations, a suitable material law is introduced. Since the sheets are formed in a semi-molten state, the material is treated as a transversely isotropic, incompressible viscous fluid reinforced with a single family of extensible fibres. Accordingly, the behaviour is characterised by three independent material parameters, namely: the longitudinal and transverse shear viscosities denoted by h_L and h_T respectively, and an elastic modulus in the fibre direction, E_L . By developing the equations of stress in an arbitrary curvilinear coordinate system, the constitutive behaviour, expressed in terms of the second Piola-Kirchhoff stress tensor, can be written as

$$T^{MN} = g^{MR} g^{NS} \left[-p C_{RS} + E_L (A^K A^L E_{KL}) A_R A_S + h_T \dot{E}_{RS} + (h_L - h_T) (A_R A^K \dot{E}_{KS} + A_S A^K \dot{E}_{KR}) \right] \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{A} is a vector identifying the fibre direction in the undeformed configuration, \mathbf{g} is the contravariant metric tensor, and \mathbf{E} and \mathbf{C} are the Lagrangian strain and deformation tensors respectively. $\dot{\mathbf{E}}$ is the strain rate tensor associated with the viscous part of the constitutive behaviour. By considering the material, or total time derivative of \mathbf{E} (in a spatial sense), allows the strain rate tensor to be developed as

$$\dot{E}_{MN} = \frac{DE_{MN}}{Dt} = \frac{\nabla E_{MN}}{\nabla t} + \frac{\nabla E_{MN}}{\nabla x^i} v^i \quad (2)$$

Under a steady state deformation the first term on the right hand side of the inequality of Eqn 2, known as the local rate of change of E_{MN} , is zero. In other words the rate of change of strain at a fixed point in space is just equal to the collective rate of change of E_{MN} , where v^i are the components of velocity for the deformed sheet. Multiplying Eqn 2 by the deformation gradient allows the strain rate tensor to be expressed as

$$\dot{E}_{MN} = \frac{\nabla E_{MN}}{\nabla X^R} V^R \quad (3)$$

where the components V^R define the velocity field in the undeformed configuration. Thus, under steady state forming conditions, the velocity gradients within the original strain rate tensor can be replaced by higher order spatial derivatives. As discussed in the paper, this has important ramifications regarding the choice of interpolating functions used in the computational model.

The constitutive law (Eqn 1), in its special steady state form, has been integrated into the computational framework of a finite element package developed at the University of Auckland. The material law has been assessed in a simple plane strain test case involving both shear and extensional deformation in the fibre direction. The stresses and deformations from this preliminary analysis have been compared to existing solutions. Having established confidence in the method, the results of a more complex 3-dimensional roll forming analysis are then presented and discussed.